

О ПРЕОБРАЗОВАНИИ НАЧАЛЬНО-КРАЕВЫХ ЗАДАЧ ИЗ ФОРМУЛИРОВКИ ДЛЯ ДРОБНЫХ ОПЕРАТОРОВ РИМАНА–ЛИУВИЛЛЯ К ФОРМУЛИРОВКЕ ОПЕРАТОРОВ КАПУТО

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EQUIVALENCE OF INITIAL CONDITIONS FOR A FRACTIONAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION WITH THE RIEMANN–LIOUVILLE DERIVATIVE

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается преобразование начально-краевых задач для дифференциальных уравнений дробного порядка из формулировки в смысле производной Римана–Лиувилля к эквивалентной постановке в смысле производной Капуто. Актуальность связана с тем, что интегральный характер условий в операторе Римана–Лиувилля усложняет анализ и применение. Исследуется связь между двумя операторами, выводятся формулы перехода и приводится пример. Показано, что использование производной Капуто позволяет задавать начальные условия в классической форме. Полученные результаты применимы в задачах математической физики, инженерии и системах с памятью.

Abstract

This paper studies the transformation of initial-boundary value problems for fractional differential equations from the Riemann–Liouville formulation to an equivalent Caputo formulation. The relevance lies in the integral nature of Riemann–Liouville initial conditions, which complicates analysis and applications. The relationship between the two operators is examined, transformation formulas are derived, and an illustrative example is provided. It is shown that the Caputo derivative enables classical initial conditions, simplifying analysis and interpretation. The results are applicable in mathematical physics, engineering, and systems with memory effects.

Ключевые слова: дробные дифференциальные уравнения, производная Римана–Лиувилля, производная Капуто, начально-краевые задачи, аналитические методы, преобразование задач.

Keywords: fractional differential equations, Riemann–Liouville derivative, Caputo derivative, initial-boundary value problems, analytical methods, problem transformation.

Introduction

In recent years, fractional calculus has become an important tool in the mathematical modeling of complex systems. Unlike classical differential equations of integer order, fractional differential equations allow the incorporation of memory and hereditary properties of various processes. This makes them particularly effective in describing real-world phenomena where the current state depends not only on present conditions but also on the entire history of the system.

Fractional calculus has become an essential tool in the modeling of complex systems with memory and hereditary properties. The theoretical foundations of fractional integrals and derivatives have been extensively developed in classical works such as those by Samko, Kilbas, and Marichev [1], as well as Podlubny [2]. Further advancements in the theory and applications of fractional differential equations have been presented in the studies by Kilbas, Srivastava, and Trujillo [3]. The importance of fractional models in describing physical processes, particularly in viscoelastic media and wave propagation, has been demonstrated by Mainardi [4]. In addition, special functions such as the Mittag-Leffler function, which play a key role in the solutions of fractional differential equations, have been thoroughly investigated by Gorenflo et al. [5]. The introduction of the Caputo fractional derivative, widely used in applied problems due to its compatibility with classical initial conditions, originates from the work of Caputo [6].

These studies form the theoretical basis for modern research in fractional differential equations and their applications.

Fractional-order models are widely used in physics, engineering, biology, and economics. They provide more accurate descriptions of anomalous diffusion, viscoelastic behavior of materials, heat transfer processes, and dynamic systems with long-term dependencies. As a result, the theory of fractional operators has developed into a significant interdisciplinary research area.

Despite the rapid progress in this field, solving initial-boundary value problems for fractional differential equations remains a challenging task. In many cases, numerical methods are applied; however, they often require substantial computational resources and may not fully reveal the qualitative structure of solutions. In contrast, analytical methods allow deeper insight into the behavior of solutions, their dependence on parameters, and the underlying properties of the model.

The purpose of this study is to develop and analyze analytical methods for solving initial-boundary value problems for differential equations with fractional operators. Special attention is given to the relationship between different definitions of fractional derivatives, particularly the transformation of problems formulated in the Riemann–Liouville sense into the Caputo form, which is more convenient for practical applications.

Problem formulation and investigating methods

1) *Equivalence of Initial Conditions for a Fractional Differential Equation with the Riemann–Liouville Derivative*

Consider the fractional differential equation with the Riemann–Liouville derivative [7]:

$$D_{a+}^{\alpha}y(x) = f(x), 0 < \alpha < 1, \quad (1)$$

where $f(x) \in L(a, b)$, and D_{a+}^{α} denotes the Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative.

The initial condition is given in the form:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a+} I_{a+}^{1-\alpha}y(x) = y_0, \quad (2)$$

where $I_{a+}^{1-\alpha}$ is the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral.

We aim to show that this condition is equivalent to the weighted limit:

$$\Gamma(\alpha) \lim_{x \rightarrow a+} (x - a)^{1-\alpha}y(x) = y_0.$$

Solution

Using the definition of the Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative:

$$D_{a+}^{\alpha}y(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{-\alpha}y(t)dt \right],$$

we apply the fractional integral operator I_{a+}^{α} to both sides of (1):

$$I_{a+}^{\alpha}D_{a+}^{\alpha}y(x) = I_{a+}^{\alpha}f(x).$$

Using known properties of fractional integrals and fractional derivatives:

$$I_{a+}^{\alpha}D_{a+}^{\alpha}y(x) = y(x) - C(x-a)^{\alpha-1},$$

where C is free constant, we obtain the general solution of (1):

$$y(x) = C(x-a)^{\alpha-1} + I_{a+}^{\alpha}f(x). \quad (3)$$

Applying the operator $I_{a+}^{1-\alpha}$ to (3):

$$I_{a+}^{1-\alpha}y(x) = I_{a+}^{1-\alpha}[C(x-a)^{\alpha-1}] + I_{a+}^1f(x).$$

Using properties of fractional integrals:

$$I_{a+}^{1-\alpha}(x-a)^{\alpha-1} = \Gamma(\alpha),$$

we obtain

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a+} I_{a+}^{1-\alpha}y(x) = C\Gamma(\alpha).$$

From the initial condition (2) we get $C = \frac{y_0}{\Gamma(\alpha)}$. Thus, the solution takes the form:

$$y(x) = \frac{y_0}{\Gamma(\alpha)}(x-a)^{\alpha-1} + I_{a+}^{\alpha}f(x).$$

Finally, considering the limit

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a+} (x-a)^{1-\alpha}y(x) = \frac{y_0}{\Gamma(\alpha)},$$

we obtain the equivalent condition:

$$\Gamma(\alpha) \lim_{x \rightarrow a+} (x-a)^{1-\alpha}y(x) = y_0.$$

It is fully equivalent to the following weighted condition:

$$\Gamma(\alpha) \lim_{x \rightarrow a+} (x-a)^{\alpha-1}y(x) = y_0.$$

2) *Cauchy Problem for a Fractional Differential Equation with the Riemann–Liouville Derivative*

Consider the Cauchy problem for a fractional differential equation with the Riemann–Liouville derivative [7]:

$$D_{0x}^{\alpha}y(x) = f(x), 0 < \alpha < 1, \quad (4)$$

with the classical initial condition:

$$y(0) = y_0.$$

Assume that the solution of (4) belongs to the class $y(x) \in C[0, l]$, $l > 0$. It is required to know that this problem is well-posed only if the right-hand side has the form $f(x) = kx^{-\alpha} + \varphi(x)$, where k is constant and $\varphi(x) \in C[0, l]$. Moreover, the initial value is not arbitrary and must satisfy:

$$y_0 = k\Gamma(1-\alpha).$$

The goal is to rewrite the initial condition in terms of $f(x)$ find the solution, and show that the smoothness condition on $\varphi(x)$ can be weakened.

Solution

Using a known property of the Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative:

$$I_{0x}^{\alpha}D_{0x}^{\alpha}y = y(x) - y(0),$$

where I_{0x}^{α} is the fractional integral operator.

Applying the fractional integral to both sides of the equation:

$$I_{0x}^{\alpha}D_{0x}^{\alpha}y = I_{0x}^{\alpha}f(x),$$

we obtain

$$y(x) - y(0) = I_{0x}^{\alpha}f(x),$$

hence,

$$y(x) = y(0) + I_{0x}^{\alpha}f(x).$$

To determine the initial condition, consider the asymptotic behavior of the fractional integral as $x \rightarrow 0+$:

$$I_{0x}^{\alpha} f(x) \sim \frac{x^{\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} f(x).$$

Therefore, $y(0) = \Gamma(1 - \alpha) \lim_{x \rightarrow 0+} x^{\alpha} f(x)$. Substituting the representation $f(x) = kx^{-\alpha} + \varphi(x)$, we obtain

$$I_{0x}^{\alpha} f = I_{0x}^{\alpha} (kx^{-\alpha}) + I_{0x}^{\alpha} \varphi(x).$$

Using the property of fractional integrals $I_{0x}^{\alpha} (x^{-\alpha}) = \Gamma(1 - \alpha)$, it follows that

$$I_{0x}^{\alpha} (kx^{-\alpha}) = k\Gamma(1 - \alpha).$$

Thus, the solution can be written as

$$y(x) = y(0) + I_{0x}^{\alpha} \varphi(x) + k\Gamma(1 - \alpha).$$

The smoothness requirement on $\varphi(x)$ can be weakened. For example, $\varphi(x) \in C(0, l) \cap L(0, l)$. In this case the condition

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0+} I_{0x}^{\alpha} \varphi(x) = 0$$

must be satisfied.

Final result

For the Cauchy problem to be well-posed, the following condition must hold

$$y(0) = \Gamma(1 - \alpha) \lim_{x \rightarrow 0+} x^{\alpha} f(x),$$

the solution of the equation is given by

$$y(x) = y(0) + I_{0x}^{\alpha} f(x).$$

Conclusion

This result shows that, for differential equations with the Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative, initial conditions can be formulated in a non-classical form. Such conditions play an important role in the theory of fractional differential equations and are widely used in the study of the solvability of initial-boundary value problems.

In this paper, two fundamental aspects of fractional differential equations with the Riemann–Liou-

ville derivative have been investigated. First, the equivalence of non-classical initial conditions with a weighted limit form has been established, which provides a more convenient representation for analytical treatment. This result clarifies the structure of initial conditions in the Riemann–Liouville framework and facilitates their interpretation.

Second, the Cauchy problem for a fractional differential equation has been analyzed. It has been shown that the well-posedness of the problem imposes specific restrictions on the right-hand side of the equation. In particular, the function must contain a singular term of power type, and the initial value is not arbitrary but determined by the asymptotic behavior of the solution.

The obtained results highlight the intrinsic differences between fractional and classical differential equations and demonstrate the importance of properly formulated initial conditions. These findings can be used in further studies of fractional models and in transforming problems into more applicable forms, such as the Caputo formulation.

References

1. Samko S. G., Kilbas A. A., Marichev O. I. *Fractional Integrals and Derivatives: Theory and Applications*. – Amsterdam: Elsevier Science, 1993. – 976 p.
2. Podlubny I. *Fractional Differential Equations*. – San Diego: Academic Press, 1999. – 340 p.
3. Kilbas A. A., Srivastava H. M., Trujillo J. J. *Theory and Applications of Fractional Differential Equations*. – Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2006. – 523 p.
4. Mainardi F. – *Fractional Calculus and Waves in Linear Viscoelasticity*. – London: Imperial College Press, 2010. – 368 p.
5. Gorenflo R., Kilbas A., Mainardi F., Rogosin S. – *Mittag-Leffler Functions, Related Topics and Applications*. – Berlin: Springer, 2014. – 443 p.
6. Michele Caputo. *Linear Models of Dissipation whose Q is Almost Frequency Independent // Geophysical Journal International*, №13, 1967. – P.529–539.
7. Огородников Е.Н., Арланова Е.Ю. *Применение аппарата дробного исчисления при решении интегральных и дифференциальных уравнений. Практикум*. – Самара: Самар.гос.техн.ун-т, 2019. – 94 с.